

Subliminal Advertising and Its Impact on Motivating and Affecting Consumers Buying Behavior

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Abstract

The research is focused mainly on how subliminal messages are manipulating the mass audiences both old and young. With many people consuming entertainment at a high level, these small changes in detail leave in imprint on the human consciousness. However, this paper is to define and explain the many different methods used. Then it also gets in-depth analysis focusing primarily on the people viewing the content with a survey highlighting on product placement and how it effects consumer behavior...Thus adding a an extra layer how advertisers convince many to buy their product without purposely shoving the product down our throats. Finally, the research paper highlights the necessary changes or propositions that need to be made in order to halt the malpractice commuted among the various fields that subliminal advertising is used in. The reason is that as the youth grows older, the separation between reality and fiction becomes a lot bigger.

Keywords: *Subliminal messages, Role of advertising, Consumer behavior, Target audience, Psychological behavior, Social integration, Subliminal perception.*

Introduction

Background

Subliminal Advertising is a conceptual based way of ads making the consumer keen in on listening to which the product is looked upon James Vicary, a market researcher, introduced subliminal advertising in the late 1950s when he inserted the phrase "Drink Coca-Cola, Eat Popcorn" during a movie. Although the words were only said for one frame, they were long enough for the subconscious mind to understand what was stated. Through this Coca-Cola had an 18.1 percent increase in sales and popcorn had an increase of 50.3 percent (Daniël H.J. Wigboldusa, Thijs Verwijmerena, Johan C. Karremansa, Wolfgang Stroebeb, April 2011). Since then, through 85 years of advertising, advertisers have added subliminal messages in their ads in order to bypass the consumers' conscious mechanisms. This phenomenon is called 'subliminal perception' which is popularized in science fiction novels and movies. A subliminal message is a visual or audio message sent quickly and subtly enough for individuals to miss it if they weren't paying attention. Numerous studies, including those in biology, psychology, and other social sciences, including management, have been the subject of subliminal message mentions. A popular study by James Vicary in the 1950s included a subliminal message in the ad. "Drink Coca-Cola and eat popcorn." The effect was an increase in post-movie sales in the refreshment box (Russel, Rowe & Smouse, 1991).

Metaphors are used in advertising that actions and messages are focusing on something otherwise, only product information such as Igniter ads, Advertising was around the bicycle. This gives you a specific thing in this ad. Examination, how employees who have purchased the recent lightning conductor of this ad? By the way, he slowed a woman who is his boss. Metaphor is this through purchase igniter you will be able to hold the girlfriend, and the other metaphor case is that you do not. You can only have girlfriends, but you will be able to keep these celebrities for others. Celebrity confirmation is mainly related to young people for their vulnerability and believes in this provision to promote fictional misunderstanding information often affects consumer behavior Determination of product or service. Determine the impact of subliminal advertising. In the field of

behavioral science People can react from the use of the developed stimulator and consumers. In addition, there are different models of consumer behavior, such as economic men who should make a reasonable decision and psychikiotic model that consumers should make a reasonable decision. It is determined by the biological drive, not a single cognitive or environmental rule. Consumers make decisions based on emotions and are not based on cognitive capabilities, are non-annual behavior that this research proposal will be studied. If the consumer's emotional ability is lower than the cognitive ability, consumers are reasonable decisions, and if he her emotional ability overcomes cognitive ability, consumer consumers are systemic it will be possible to make this inconvenience decision. When you do this, this will lead to buy power. This is mainly due to external attraction as an internal factor or sublime. Display and here focus on taking into account the impact of subliminal exposure to internal aspects such as realization, affection, advertising evaluation, and advertising participation. In order to achieve further advances in this direction, it was also considered to determine the impact of emotions and emotions caused by sublimation exposure to young consumers' purchase behavior.

Problem statement

The debate over subliminal tactics began as early as the 1950s and is also used to increase sales and change consumer behavior, a phenomenon that is widespread in today's situation. Additionally, subliminal messages can lead to anxiousness, which is why people often turn to smoking, drugs, and binge eating to calm them down. Sending one-to-one or one-to-one messages is the concept of persuasion. Subliminal beliefs occur when people can successfully instill a message in individuals or groups of people seeking change without consciously assessing change, and are encouraged to organically convey their ideas to colleagues. The goal of subliminal beliefs is to influence people's thoughts, beliefs, and acceptance of new information—not just as true, but also as essential to its dissemination. To entice potential customers, subliminal persuasion is used in advertising, marketing, filmmaking, public relations, publicity, bargaining, and religion.

Significance of the Study

The effectiveness of subliminal advertising has been a subject of much discussion. To what extent this kind of advertisement truly influences a person's emotional and cognitive aspects and compels them to make a purchase. This research proposal describes some aspects of customer behavior that may be affected by subliminal advertising, such as emotions, potential involvement in portrayed behavior, and confidence in the behavior and ideas promoted by these advertising. I tried to find out if sex, whether such ads cause confusion, or if they are compulsory. Purchase habits, purchase intent, privacy at the time of purchase (Moore, 1982).

Advertising is important not only to advertisers, but also to consumers. Advertising serves as a vital information source for consumers and a means of generating sales for advertisers. Because the messages contained in the products are more spiritual than visual, advertisers exploit the ignorance of prospective customers by igniting their mental states with the feelings and emotions that cause them to purchase the product. I am always enthusiastic about it. In addition, research on advertising effectiveness has shown that the attractiveness of advertising (both emotionally and logically) has a positive effect on advertising attitudes and buying intentions. According to the same study, consumers tend to focus on emotionally compelling messages and less on rational appeal such as information and quality (Moore, 1982). Consumers can be persuaded subtly in a number of ways, such as through background music, background language, a message of love, social evidence, or cult feeling, however this can go against good business ethics. As a result, the following issues must be resolved: B. Is it reasonable to have so much porn that the majority of the advertisements are obvious? How about semi-sexual acts? How morally acceptable is the use of metaphors in marketing, and more significantly, how moral is the use of celebrity endorsements? As a result, the majority of recent study has concentrated on three types of advertising: pornography and semi-sexual behavior, metaphors, and celebrity backing. Advertising, including sexual content, can help promote items, but its side effects, such as trends and awakenings, can deceive young viewers into thinking that they can fulfil their biological demands through illicit partnerships. There are and cause fear and anxiety Stress can force them to get addicted to drugs if they catch them in a vicious circle.

Literature Review

Visual or audio information that are conveyed too rapidly or too subtly for individuals to notice are known as subliminal messages. Subliminal messaging literally means "below the threshold." In the domains of biology and other social sciences, research into subliminal messaging is ongoing. For example, Cheesman and Merikle (1986) used the concept of psychodynamic activation to explain how subliminal messages affect a person. According to this theory, subliminal messages stimulate the visual or auditory cortex of the brain while the conscious mind may be ignorant of it. In accordance with this theory, a subliminal message enters a person's subconscious directly, bypassing the conscious mind's gatekeeper. In a press release, James Vicary, a researcher by profession, asserted that subliminal messages encouraged moviegoers to purchase Coca-Cola and popcorn (Packard & Miller, 1957). He projected the words Drink Coca-Cola and Eat Popcorn for 1/3,000 of a second at five-second intervals during the showing of the movie "Picnic" using a method known as the tachistoscope. Subliminal messaging came to the attention of the corporate community soon after the Coca-Cola study. Related scientific initiatives have received federal funding (Russel et al., 1991). Subliminal messages are perceived by the general public and academics as a medium that subtly encourages deviant behaviors in children, youngsters, and teenagers, such as early sexual stimulation.

Subliminal Perception

A person's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors can be influenced by a variety of stimuli without that person being aware of it. This concept is known as subliminal perception. Supraliminal stimuli are the stimuli that the brain is conscious of receiving (Weber, 2010.) The inability to express subliminal perception verbally results from its failure to enter consciousness. Because a person has a higher probability of being influenced by others when they are younger (Milia & Nikoli, 2013), this is particularly true for children and young people. Even adults struggle to understand all verbal and nonverbal cues in daily life. In order for young people to differentiate between fact and fiction, media pedagogy must enable the discovery of subliminal impulses. The best examples are children's movies and animated cartoons. They are a part of every child's life. The subliminal perception operates covertly and does not require the hidden information presented in movies to immediately enter awareness (Toli, Vertovek, & Milia, 2009). Children, for instance, are consciously aware of all the details in a certain scenario when they are shown a visual scene. The difference is only "processed" by them, not necessarily experienced on a conscious level, if a little detail changes in the background (which typically happens very rapidly). Do things alter? It depends on the viewer's attention to determine what is processed on a conscious or unconscious level (Tolich, Vertovshek, & Milisha, 2009). In this regard, different aspects of animated movies and other media content (cultural, educational). Every area of human life is subject to consumer influence. Although it is unethically wrong to do so, many different sectors nonetheless employ this approach. Advertising has an impact on the economy and on how consumers are manipulated. political voters Brainwashing is one type of manipulation. Manipulation takes on the form of a state-run entertainment enterprise in the leisure sector.

Subliminal messages

The subliminal messages are those that travel below the threshold of human perception. They are invisible to the human eye and psyche. Since 89 percent of human action is unconscious, it is important to consider the possibilities of affecting that part. Some authors (Egermann, Kopiez & Reuter, 2006) define subliminal messages as a signal or message inserted into another object. The intention is to bypass the normal boundaries of perception or as "any situation in which unnoticed stimuli are perceived"(Egermann, Kopiez, & Reuter, 2006).

The respondents gave higher ratings to those whose photographs were connected to emotionally favorable imagery than to others, despite not being cognizant of these associations. When people followed after subliminally offered and consciously ignored kittens, their features appeared more endearing than when they did so after subliminally presented and consciously ignored corpses. Sex was the original and oldest instance of a subliminal message. The most frequent word and image in subliminal communications is "sex." For instance,

the word "sex" is printed in the upper right corner of the palm leaves on the Seychelles 50 rupee banknote. Only if you look closely will you see it. A comparable instance may be seen in the Disney animated film "The Lion King," where the word "sex" is briefly written in the sky. The most common term in goods and service advertisements is "sex." However, subliminal messages are not only used in the consumerism industry. According to Ran Hassin studies, they are used in political campaigns to influence the electorate (Hassin & Sklar, 2014). In particular, the subconscious use of national symbols, like flags, has an impact on political opinions and voting behavior. The impact of subliminal signals on people's consciousness is undeniable, even though their influence has not yet been objectively proven. Two parts make up the human brain. The cognitive and analytical processes of the nervous system are controlled by the left side of the brain. The subconscious, emotions, and instinct, on the other hand, are handled by the right side. As a result, the secret message is undetectable to the left side of the brain, which does not understand it, but becomes a command to the right. The research conducted by psychologists Strahan, Spencer and Zanna in 2002 explored the influence of subliminal messages on peoples thirstiness. They assembled a group and conducted an experiment. The centre of the screen was required of the responders to focus on. In a single second, words like thirsty, dry, and dehydrated appeared on the screen. According to the study, the messages on the screen had almost no impact on the group members who did not feel thirsty. On the contrary, the party arrived a little bit thirsty, but they were instructed to refrain from drinking for the following three hours. The findings of the study in this section indicated that subliminal messages had a substantial impact on and exacerbated the thirst sensation. At the conclusion of the study, each participant was given a glass of juice as a treat. The experiment to measure how thirsty a person was also included this juice glass. Some of the thirsty individuals drank far more than the rest. According to the study, subliminal messages are unable to sufficiently evoke particular feelings, intents, or motivations to alter behavior.

However, if people are already motivated or feeling something, these subliminal messages can be considerably strengthened. Later, in 2006, psychologists Karremans, Stroebe, and Claus theorized that subliminal messaging might intensify a specific emotion, such as how thirst can influence people's support for a particular producer. The experiment used Lipton iced tea as an illustration. By splitting the respondents into two groups—one with thirst and the other without—the researchers were able to use a portion of the 2002 study. Respondents were asked to concentrate in the centre of the screen, while Lipton logos and photos of their iced tea were displayed separately within three hundredths, as in the prior study. The researchers gave the participants two choices of iced tea at the conclusion of the experiment: one was Lipton and the other came from an unidentified manufacturer. There is evidence that those who responded to the survey preferred Lipton iced tea when they were already thirsty. According to the poll, subliminal signals have the ability to influence people's behaviour in order to satisfy unmet demands. They can not only enhance a specific feeling but can also direct people in a certain path. In 2013, psychologists Gibson and Zielaskowski (2013) researched a Las Vegas casino where they inserted thumbnails showing a US dollar symbol or a jackpot message on second-hand clips on slot machines. When these messages were displayed to some customers, they bet and gambled 55 percent more than other casino patrons did. After being exposed to subliminal messages about winning, roughly 45 percent of respondents were certain they would win something. Additionally, respondents stated that they felt the need to increase their financial investments. Studies reveal that the ideal set of circumstances contributed to the potency of subconscious messages.

Role of advertising

It is distinguished by a crucial emphasis on visual cues, such as facial expressions, body language, and gestures. Advertising to a large extent reflects the social values, predominate conventions, beliefs, and prejudices of a culture. The majority of the time, images used in advertising has a significant impact on how society views sexuality, the "ideal life," and conventions and values (Polly, 1993). The mass communication tools that are easily available to marketers are advertising, sales promotion, and public relations. The term "mass communication" refers to the use of the same message by all members of the target audience. The Mass Media tools trade off the advantage of personal selling. Etzel in 1997 proclaimed that it provides an opportunity to

adapt a message for each prospect and benefits in reaching a number of people at a lower cost per person (Etzel, 1997).

Subliminal marketing and marketing is a method that reveals the patron, with out their knowledge, to snap shots of merchandise and manufacturers. Once uncovered to a subliminal stimulus, the patron is convinced that they apprehend the information. The maximum arguable region inside subliminal psychological strategies is "subliminal persuasion", which suggests the direct effect of subliminal strategies on patron behavior. Weber (2010) became inquisitive about locating approaches to include subliminal stimuli into commercials to steer destiny behaviour.

Advertising and marketing managers took notice of subliminal marketing after James Vicary's experiment with popcorn and Coca-Cola. Since then, numerous studies on the efficiency of marketing and subliminal messaging have been carried out (Key, 1992). There are some illogical aspects to some customer behaviour. The customer is guided by their aspirations and reacts to their impact. In nature, each person is required to identify themselves with a symbol, which somehow becomes a part of the individual's personality.

Why does the patron purchase a unique form of TV? Which elements are vital at some point of that selection? The cost, screen size, style, or repute of the logo? There are numerous unique manufacturers with a tonne of added features. Due to the fact that certain manufacturers have completely different target markets, only one brand sells more TVs than the others. The same tests showed that a customer will only make their final decision after carefully weighing all of their possibilities (Miliša & Nikolić, 2013). Both internal and external stimuli, such as those imposed by the media environment, have an impact on it (Schiffman, Kanuk & Fridl, 2004). Subliminal stimuli's emotional content will affect different people differently depending on who they are used to. For instance, Theus (1994) came to the conclusion that neurotic people prefer to use neutral sentences in a methodical manner rather than those having emotional depth. People that exhibit significantly less repression, additional passivity, and greater flexibility in reporting, and significantly less hostility are significantly more likely to process subliminal cues. Additionally, studies have shown that the deeper subliminal inputs are, the more powerfully they can influence a person. As a stimulus gets closer to the supraliminal level, its energy will rise. A similar finding was reached by Bornstein, Leone, and Galley (1987). They underline how after repeated exposure to the same stimulus, the subject's relationship to the new stimulus becomes more pleasant. The most important thing is that instinctual devices should be equipped to receive subliminal stimuli. Given how strongly instincts influence people; this will lead to an increased effectiveness of subliminal techniques. The ability to make sense of a large number of external stimuli depends on a variety of factors, including the relative depth of the stimulus content, the magnitude of that content, time duration, changes in movement, the dynamics of the content, the contrast of the content, the repetition of the stimulus, prior experience, habits, attitudes, motivation, interests, desires, and expectations. Subliminal stimuli may be intended to evoke either a strong or a weaker response, as discovered in 1982 by Riggs, Volkmann, Moore, and Ellicott. Years have been spent researching the relationship between subliminal stimuli and symbol preference. The findings demonstrated that subliminal advertising may have an instant impact on a customer's preference for a brand and changes in future behavior. Changes in feelings, behavior, values, and instincts can also be prompted by subliminal inputs.

In Pakistan, consumer awareness has reached high peaks thanks to mass media, specifically a number of television channels and online social media. As a result, the efficiency of subliminal advertisements is constantly rising. The majority of Pakistani consumers, particularly teenagers in metropolitan areas, are politically and socially conscious of daily events. The effectiveness of advertising has still not been the subject of any serious research. Malik did a small study on the impact of subliminal advertising in connection to the purchasing behaviour of female university students in 1999 (Malik, 1999).

Social Integration

A platform for the improvement of the consumer's self-image is provided by subliminal advertising (Richins, 1991). With that, it also gives the product meaning, with many of the potential customers paying premium costs for branded goods that have well-known trademarks and eye-catching corporate designs (Polly, 1993). The use of advertising as a technique may prove to be highly important for the growth of a consumer's sense of self and

personal style. As a result, the advertising that is related gains a favorable reputation. Additionally, the Social Comparison Theory has allowed marketers to examine a number of phenomena, such as the comparison of physical beauty to promoted models, evaluation of the connected material belongings, and consumer sensitivity to social comparison statistics (Richins, 1991). The greater part of the promoting studies has distinguished the earlier justification for correlation with be self-assessment (Festinger, 1954). Besides, three thought processes have been distinguished in the social brain research including: self-assessment, self-upgrade and personal growth. Talking as far as promoting, the subconscious publicizing models act as a benchmark for the ideal picture of excellence so the correlation made will in general be vertical. This implies that the customers believe publicizing models to be predominant as far as actual appeal with any of the three thought processes referenced above could be served through vertical examinations (Martin, 1993). Nonetheless, it could likewise be the situation that vertical correlations with the promoting models may not end up being self-improving because of closeness on the prompt aspects like age(a few models are in their twenties) or the specific circumstance(the model isn't a school mate). So when self-improvement will in general be the principal wellspring of examination, female preadolescents and teenagers won't make up correlations against the promoting models. This will help them in settling their mythical being regard. In the new times, the greater part of the specialists have applied Thematic Apperception Test sketch (TAT), a kind of a projective method that was applied to an example of female teenagers to assess the overwhelming thought process that arises while contrasting oneself with publicizing models. Then again, many advertising scientists utilized TATs to find the individual prepping ceremonies of the shoppers (Richins, 1991). The potential watchers that create innovative stories regarding a pictorial upgrade will uncover different secret parts of their ongoing worries, inspirations and perspectives on the world. This, thus, recognizes the basic reason (Richins, 1991).

In Pakistan, the middle, top focus and the tip top superbness are at risk to marked items. These are in actuality the bad-to-the-bone logo unswerving buyers of administrations and items that're leaned to offer any charge as extended in light of the fact that the extraordinary issue isn't compromised 100% of the time. A large portion of the ads like that of Olpers, Mobilink and National Foods instill the social issue of the Pakistani society. As the necessities of dwelling improve, the issue of social mix will take additional promotion and buyers could least difficult eat up the ones administrations and items which can be broadly predominant among their buddies and family. This perspective has seldom been perceived with inside the past investigates with appreciate to Pakistan and sorting out it, could cause higher information on the assessment norms of the buyers while they might be uncovered to assorted subconscious media advertisements.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework:

Research objectives

1. To find out the difference between consumers perception of the subliminal messages and consumer behavior.
2. To determine the impact of the emotions evoked by the subliminal messages towards consumer behavior.
3. To analyze the effect of product placement on consumer behavior
4. To find out the difference between the medium of advertising and consumer behavior

Research questions

1. What is the relationship between consumer perception of the subliminal messages and consumer behavior?
2. What is the impact of the emotions evoked by the subliminal messages towards consumer behavior?
3. What is the effect of product placement on consumer behavior?
4. What is the relationship between the medium of advertising and consumer behavior

Hypothesis

H₁: there is a significant impact of the consumers' perception of the subliminal messages on consumer behavior

H₂: there is a significant impact of the emotions evoked by the subliminal messages on consumer behavior

H₃: there is a significant impact of product placement on consumer behavior

H₄: there is a significant impact of the medium of advertising on consumer behavior

Methodology

The rational methodology is taken on to accomplish the goals of this review. Inside the extent of this exploration, we were are just keen on responding to the examination question, which was figured out from a hypothesis of general substance; are people mindful of subconscious prompts and do they think that they are moral. The inspecting was comfort testing since the populace is huge. We utilized the virtual snowball testing since we involved virtual interpersonal organizations for arriving at the respondents. This technique was picked in light of the fact that it's quick, straightforward, and practical. The study was sent by means of informal organization Facebook and versatile application WhatsApp. A review was ship off people who then passed it to their contacts until we accomplished a good number of reactions.

Online Survey

The creators utilized web-based reviews to investigate whether respondents know about subtle prompts and what is their perspective about utilizing them; is it moral or unscrupulous and do they impact their way of behaving. The poll was made on the google structures stage. It was a mysterious internet based review. This technique was utilized in light of the fact that it is rapid and cheap. A presentation part was introduced toward the beginning of the poll to provide members an unmistakable thought of the motivation of the review.

Inclusion criteria

There are no explicit inclusion criteria, and anyone is welcome to participate. The survey was distributed to the general population of Karachi via WhatsApp.

Results and discussion

Demographic profile

what is your age?
64 responses

Figure 2: Age

64 people responded to the survey, of whom 12.5% were under the age of 18, 65.6% were between the ages of 18 and 25, 10.9% were between the ages of 26 and 35, 4.7% were between the ages of 36 and 45, 1.6% were between the ages of 46 and 55, and 4.7% were responses from respondents over the age of 55.

what is your gender?
64 responses

Figure 3: Gender

53.1% of respondents were males whereas 46.9% of respondents were females.

where do you prefer to shop?
64 responses

Figure 4: shop preference

According to the survey, 45.3% of the respondents were those who prefer to shop online and 54.7% where those who prefer to shop offline.

how much do you approximately spend on shopping each month

64 responses

Figure 5: shopping expenditure

According to the survey, 53.1% of the respondents were people whose total expenditure on shopping is less than 20,000Rs, 20.3% were those who spend approximately between 20,000Rs-50,000Rs, 14.1% were those who spend approximately between 50,000Rs-100,000Rs, 7.8% were those who spend approximately between 100,000Rs-200,000Rs, and 4.7% of the respondents were those who spend above 200,000Rs

Data analysis

Table1:

Age:

Ranks			
	what is your age?	N	Mean Rank
Subliminal_Advertising	Under 18	8	33.63
	18-25	42	32.37
	26-35	7	32.43
	36-45	3	56.33
	46-55	1	6.50
	6	3	16.33

As the table suggests, People of diverse ages are equally affected by subliminal advertising, with no noticeable difference between them.

Table 2:

Gender:

Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
		Subliminal_Advertising	
Subliminal_Advertising	Male	34	37.87
	female	30	26.42
	Total	64	
Kruskal-Wallis H		6.067	
df		1	
Asymp. Sig.		.014	

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: what is your gender?

According to the data, subliminal advertising is more likely to have an impact on females.

Table 3:
Shopping preference

Ranks			
	where do you prefer to shop?	N	Mean Rank
Subliminal_Advertising	online	29	32.86
	offline	35	32.20

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	Subliminal_Advertising
Kruskal-Wallis H	.020
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.887

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping variable: where do you prefer to shop.

Similarly, the likelihood that a person will be influenced by subliminal advertising is unaffected by whether they prefer to shop online or in person.

Table 4:

Ranks			
	how much do you approximately spend on shopping each month	N	Mean Rank
Subliminal_Advertising	less than 20,000	34	34.00
	20,000-50,000	13	27.08
	50,000-100,000	9	35.61
	100,000-200,000	5	27.70
	5	3	37.67
	Total	64	

According to the data, the respondents monthly expenditure does not have an impact on how likely they are to be affected by subliminal advertising

Descriptive analysis

The data shows that no matter what whether, age, shopping preference, or monthly expenditure there is no significant difference in terms of how likely they are to be influenced by subliminal advertising. However, there is a significant difference when it comes to gender.

Reliability analysis

Table 5:

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	64	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	64	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

The summary shows that all the data collected was valid and no data were excluded. This gives the data a hundred per cent (100%) reliability. With the results being reliable, the results are now ready for further analysis.

Table 6:

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.704	10

The reliability statistics shows that there is no significant difference

Conclusion

From the survey we deduced, that 64 people responded to the survey, of whom 12.5% were under the age of 18, 65.6% were between the ages of 18 and 25, 10.9% were between the ages of 26 and 35, 4.7% were between the ages of 36 and 45, 1.6% were between the ages of 46 and 55, and 4.7% were responses from respondents over the age of 55. People of diverse ages are equally affected by subliminal advertising, with no noticeable difference between them. The data shows that no matter what whether, age, shopping preference, or monthly expenditure there is no significant difference in terms of how likely they are to be influenced by subliminal advertising. However, there is a significant difference when it comes to gender.

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